

VR Conferencing: communicating and collaborating in photo-realistic social immersive environments

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ABSTRACT

While Virtual Reality applications become more multi-user experiences, mostly artificial avatars are used for the representation of users in the virtual environment. This is fine for many multi-user scenarios but is less than ideal in more social settings like talking to your family, friends or business partners. In this paper, we like to outline the concept of Social VR based on real-time photorealistic capture and representation of users. Particularly, we introduce our web-based framework that allows for both the creation and consumption of photo-realistic social VR in 3D and 360-degree environments. Further, we evaluated our system both in a 360-degree remote collaborative meeting and in a full 3D experience. Our initial results indicate that our photo-realistic approach indeed offers a natural communication to the users with a high presence and immersion. With our system we do not only allow to explore, and experience VR together but also allow new forms of remote communication and collaboration.

Keywords

Virtual Reality, VR, Social VR, WebRTC, WebVR, interactive content, immersive virtual environments.

1. SOCIAL VR

Nowadays, social VR is mostly associated with graphical avatars in a graphical environment. Main examples are Facebook Spaces¹, AltSpaceVR², Mozilla Hubs³ and many more. All these consist of a shared virtual environment, using graphical avatars to represent the users, and offering various possibilities, such as shared gaming and content consumption and multi-user communication and collaboration. The transfer of user motion to avatar motion is achieved by employing HMD and controller tracking. These environments offer a compelling experience of togetherness in which immersive video is combined with spatial and 3D audio [5], still, they are limited in the way you perceive other users. “The social cues that you would normally have about someone being creepy or safe weren’t there.” [3]

The alternative to a graphical avatar is a photo-realistic representation of users. When it comes to photo-realistic social VR we can distinguish between 3 types: i) capturing the user and environment at the same time (e.g. with omni-directional cameras), ii) capturing the user alone (e.g. with depth or stereo

Figure 1: multi user 360-degree experience

cameras) [1][2][4][6] and iii) capturing a full (volumetric) 3D representation of the user [7]. However, due to the complexity of processing and transmission of 360-degree and volumetric data the first and third approaches still need more research to get closer to market ready. Our approach focuses on an individual user capture via RGB and depth sensors. This offers the benefit of being able to reuse traditional media processing and transmission and thus having a reliable end-to-end media chain.

2. TOGETHER VR

Our social VR framework called Together VR extends current video conferencing with new VR functionalities, based on web standards and technologies. The framework is modular and allows for an easy creation of VR experiences that are social and the consumption of these experiences, using off-the-shelf hardware. With the framework, we aim to allow users to interact and collaborate while being immersed in interactive VR content.

To capture a photorealistic representation of a user, we first need to capture a color and depth image with the help of a depth camera (e.g. Microsoft Kinect v2 or Intel Realsense). In a second step the image is analyzed, and the user is separated from the background (the background is replaced with a chroma-key color). The resulting image is transmitted via a web client as video over WebRTC to another user’s web client. Finally, the complete virtual environment is rendered in the browser and the users are placed into the environment (making the chroma-key background transparent) so that he/she naturally blends into the surroundings.

Each end-point consists of a VR capable laptop, a single depth camera, audio headset and a VR HMD.

¹ <https://www.facebook.com/spaces>

² <https://altvr.com/>

³ <https://hubs.mozilla.com/>

Figure 2: Social VR 3D-degree experience (incl. self-view)

3. MULTI-USER 360-DEGREE EXPERIENCE

In our multi-user 360-degree experience [2][4], 2-4 people sit around a table in VR. The view of each user is the same, each user sees the other users on the opposite side of the table and optionally a video or presentation on the top of the table (see Figure 1). To evaluate this experience, we held a 1-day experiment session in an informal and uncontrolled setting at our lab facilities, asking groups of 3 people to communicate while watching a video. We collected feedback through a short questionnaire from 54 participants (avg. age of 33 and 43% Female). People expressed a high level of interaction and immersion within the conversations. As part of the questionnaire the users rated the system with a “good” overall quality of 4.35 (SD 0.51) and video quality of 3.65 (SD 0.77) on a 5-point scale.

4. MULTI-USER FULL 3D EXPERIENCE

In our full 3D experience (see Figure 2), we include a full 3D environment and use both the color and depth information of the user capture to display users in 3D (as point cloud or mesh). This means, additionally to the replacement of the background with a chroma, a new image format combines the color image and the depth image. This is, we map the depth image into a grayscale and transmit the image as 2D video. To display this image as a point cloud or mesh we developed an optimized WebGL shader that maps each pixel into the 3D coordinates of the space [1]. This approach is also used to display a self-representation to each user. To evaluate this experience, we held a 2-day experiment session in an informal and uncontrolled setting at a conference venue. We collected feedback through a short questionnaire from 25 participants (avg. age of 35,26 and 12% Female) where 2 people were asked to communicate in our system while switching the environment between a 3D and a 360-degree virtual space. As part of the questionnaire, people expressed a preference for the 3D experience (60% 3D, 28% 2D, 12 % no clear preference) with a “good” overall quality of 6.92 (SD: 1.55) on a 9-point scale.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Overall, our current social VR web framework offers the possibility to easily create photo-realistic social VR experiences with a good user experience and natural interactions. It also allows to evaluate different types of VR technology and to quickly extend the software components with new functionalities.

Our next steps in development will focus on the following:

- Eye-gaze: to look each other in the eye. This year we will have a first version that replaces the HMD in a user representation with a photorealistic model of the face.
- Scalability: allowing large groups of people to join one session. This year we will scale our system to allow up to 10 users in one communication session, using a VR conferencing bridge.
- AR and mobility. As both augmented reality and mobile devices are becoming more important we are currently investigating how to extend and map our current framework to support AR and mobile display devices.
- Long term trials. We are currently setting up long term trials allowing people to use our system in their normal work environment for remote collaboration and meetings.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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